

Amplify the performance and stability of perovskite solar cells using fluorinated salt as the surface passivator

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Abstract: Three-dimensional hybrid perovskite-based solar cells have shown outstanding power conversion efficiency, while layered perovskite is emerging as the advanced version to deliver high stability. Galvanize with the surge of the report of layered perovskites, we explore a common salt tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF) as a passivating agent between perovskite and hole transporting layer that improves the power conversion efficiency and stability. The use of TBAPF as a surface passivator mitigates the surface defect and increases hydrophobicity. The fluorine atoms in TBAPF provide hydrogen bonding interaction with the hydrogen of organic ammonium cation in perovskite established by nuclear magnetic resonance techniques (¹H-NMR). Effective charge extraction to the hole transport layer is suggested by steady-state photoluminescence (PL) measurements, showing higher quenching with the passivated perovskite compared to the pristine perovskite. Our results suggest TBAPF treatment improved the junction quality and minimizes the defects by virtue of the H-bonding, which in turn improves the photovoltaic parameters and long-term stability.

Introduction

Hybrid halide perovskites are actively being researched owing to their outstanding performance in light-emitting devices,^[1] photodetectors,^[2] field-effect transistor (FET),^[3] laser,^[4] water-splitting,^[5] and solar cells.^[6] The efficient energy conversion in solar cells is being seen as a viable alternative to replace fossil fuels besides space exploration.^[7]

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) enjoy wide spectral absorption and high power conversion efficiency (PCE) while other emerging solar cells suffer from a narrow spectral response.^[8] However, the stability under operational conditions remains a major drawback to the commercialization of PSCs.^[6c,9] Among all perovskites, the organic-inorganic perovskites with the general formula ABX₃ (A= methyl ammonium (MA) and formamidinium (FA); B= Pb²⁺ or Sn²⁺; and X= Cl, I, Br)^[6] not only have flexible properties of organic compound, but also tuneable properties of inorganic compound.^[10] 3-dimensional organic-inorganic perovskites have shown PCE of over 25.7% due to their excellent optoelectronic properties.^[11] However, organic cations such as MA, and FA are sensitive to processing conditions and tend to be less crystalline. Mixing inorganic cation cesium (Cs) with organic perovskites such as FA and MA provides a cation pool with high surface quality and purity in PSCs.^[12] Grätzel *et al.* used inorganic Cs together with FA and MA and the formulated perovskite showed improved stability, with fewer phase impurities and a PCE of 21.1%.^[13] Seok *et al.* disclosed that substituting small, equimolar amounts of Cs and methylene diammonium cations in FA sites reduced the lattice strain and trap densities together with increasing in open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and led to a certified PCE of 24.4%.^[14] By reducing the dimensions of perovskite from 3D to Two-dimensional (2D), the electronic bandgap increases from the optimum value for PV (photovoltaics) applications, and the PV

parameters decreases because of low carrier transport, and low absorption coefficient.^[15] Layered organic-inorganic perovskite (2D) is recognized for its stability due to the presence of the spacer such as organic *n*-butyl ammonium (BA) spacer, which is sandwiched between the inorganic layers and increases the stability of perovskite. Also, the stability roots from a factor which is strong van der Waals interaction between alkyl chains and [PbI₆]⁻ units^[16]. Nevertheless, the aliphatic organic spacer cation hinders vertical charge transport and decreases PCE. To increase the PCE in layered perovskites, Tsai *et al.* reported a hot-casting technique. This technique delivered a compact and uniform thin film with a larger grain size for perovskite as compared to the room temperature-casting technique and delivered a PCE of 12.52%.^[17] The experimental and computational techniques showed that improved performance was related to reducing bulk defects and improved charge carrier mobility due to large grains. By increasing the perovskite grain size, the non-radiative recombination decreases because of the covering of defects in the boundaries, yet the defects on the surface will remain largely unchanged.^[18] Wang *et al.* reported using Li⁺ as the dopant helps to increase carrier mobility for (BA)₂(MA)₃Pb₄I₁₃ perovskite materials which resulted in the reduction of the trap density states, and a higher PCE of ≈15%.^[19] Huang *et al.* introduced 2-(methyl thio) ethyl amine hydrochloride (MTEACI) instead of BA in layered perovskites resulting in enhanced charge transport and stabilization. The author reported the new bulky alkyl ammonium is responsible for high stability and a certified PCE of 17.8%.^[20]

By considering the efforts made for increasing the PCE in layered perovskite, 3D perovskite still displays higher PCE while they suffer from instability.^[21] Thus, improving stability in 3D perovskite, by the inspiration of the lewis bases which trigger stability in layered perovskite can guide us toward the fabrication of PSCs with high stability and performance. Using large organic chains as the passivating agent not only stops ion migration from perovskite to HTM but also works as a blocking layer against the volatility of FA and MA.^[22] Phenyl ethyl ammonium chloride (PEACI) in perovskite resulted in enhanced phase purity and stability. The perovskite films with high crystallinity, large grain size, and low trap densities were attributed to Cl anion in PEACI while passivation of the defects at the perovskite surface via electrostatic interactions is attributed to the PEA cations (PEA⁺). The authors noted that hydrophobic phenyl rings increase moisture resistance.^[23]

Grätzel *et al.* modified the surface of methyl ammonium lead triiodide (MAPbI₃) by spin-coating in the presence of butyl phosphonic acid 4-ammonium chloride. Various analyses showed that the phosphonic acid ammonium additive plays a role as a crosslink between grains in the perovskite through hydrogen bonding of the -PO(OH)₂ and -NH₃⁺ terminal groups on the perovskite surface which resulted in a PCE of 16.7%.^[24] Moreover, it has been reported fluorinated cations can upgrade the performance and stability of PSCs.^[25] A hydrophobic fluorinated organic salt called pentafluoro-propylammonium iodide (PFPAI) was reported to modulate the surface and

electronic properties of 3D perovskite. The maximum PCE of 16.4% along with high stability was obtained using an optimized concentration (200 mM) of PFPAl. [26] Snaith *et al.* used an ionic liquid called 1-butyl-3-methyl imidazolium tetra-fluoroborate (BMIMBF₄, 1.2 mol%) as an additive into perovskite resulting in higher efficiency of 19.8% and improved long-term device stability. [27] Recently, our group also used a thin layer of an aromatic compound called fluoro-phenethyl ammonium iodide (FPEAI) as a passivator over the 3-D perovskite and an optimized concentration of FPEAI (3% w/v) exhibited a higher PCE of 20.63% due to reduced non-radiative carrier recombination, and higher stability than the control device. [28]

Jiu *et al.* spin-coated 1H-Pyrazole-1-carboxamide hydrochloride (PAH) on the formamidinium lead iodide (FAPbI₃) film to passivated defects sites at room temperature. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) showed there is an interaction between PAH and surface Pb ions reducing the trap states and increasing the device performance. The passivated device delivered a PCE of 20.9%, together with enhancement of V_{oc} and fill factor (FF). [29]

Various multifunctional molecules founding chelidamic acid (5 mg/mL) have the best dipolar electron density distribution among others to passivated defects sites in MAPbI₃. The passivated PSCs showed a PCE of 19.06% with a V_{oc} of 1.09 V while also maintaining 63% of the initial efficiency under 1-sun illumination at 100 °C for 60 h while the pristine PSC showed the performance dropped to 22% of the initial performance in 20 h. [30] These organic salts reported are not straightforward to synthesize and are expensive. Here we report our findings with the use of a classical aliphatic organic salt called tetra-n-butyl ammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF), equipped with four low volatile BA cation and hydrophobic hexa-fluoro phosphate (PF₆) anion as the passivating agent for 3-D halide perovskite. The photovoltaic parameters show the fluorinated organic salt not only decreases the defect on the surface of the perovskite but also increases the hydrophobicity due to the fluorinated anion.

Results and Discussion

We used the triple cation Cs_{0.1}(FA_{0.9}MA_{0.1})_{0.9}Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})₃, called CsFAMA perovskite as a light absorber for device fabrication. It shows a λ_{max} at 755 nm while there is no change in the intensity of perovskite after passivation (Figure 1a). This result shows that TBAPF thin film does not have any adverse effect on the optical properties of CsFAMA. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed to examine the crystallinity of the perovskite which is covered by TBAPF thin film (Figure 1b). The result shows there is no change in the diffraction pattern and no shifting in the position of XRD peaks. The peaks at $2\theta = 14.24^\circ, 20.09^\circ, 24.65^\circ, 28.46^\circ, 31.90^\circ, 35.05^\circ, 40.63^\circ,$ and 43.23° represent the typical diffraction peaks of (101), (012), (021), (202), (211), (122), (024), and (131) planes, respectively. [12b] The absence of any peaks below $2\theta = 10^\circ$ suggests the passivation molecule did not penetrate the perovskite to act as the insulator and form the layered perovskite. [26]

Figure 1. a) UV-vis absorbance spectra, b) XRD pattern of a thin layer of pristine CsFAMA (Black) and with TBAPF (Red), Surface SEM image of (c) CsFAMA, and (d) CsFAMA-TBAPF (1mM) with a scale bar of 500 nm.

The microstructure of the perovskite and the passivated one are recorded using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The CsFAMA film exhibits a uniform surface morphology without any pinhole (Figure 1c). After passivation, the perovskite grains are more compact and a homogenous surface is observed (Figure 1d) some small TBAPF crystals can be seen on grain boundaries. In the higher concentration of TBAPF (2mM) these small crystals are more visible and are presented in Figure S1.

Further, to investigate the chemical interaction between the TBAPF and perovskite, we performed proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹HNMR), which is a powerful technique to investigate the chemical interaction between molecules. [31] The CsFAMA and CsFAMA-TBAPF films on the glass were dissolved in deuterated DMSO solution and ¹HNMR measurements were performed (Figures 2a and b). As can be seen, after passivation the hydrogen peaks of FA (H^a & H^b) at 8.67 and 8.97 ppm shifted to 8.65 and 8.99 ppm, this type of interaction between FA and the other counter ions has been reported previously. [32] Interestingly, after the passivation of CsFAMA with TBAPF, the singlet peak of FA (H^b) at 7.84 ppm did not shift (Figure 2b).

These results unambiguously suggest hydrogen bonding interaction between TBAPF and H^a of FA on the surface of perovskite causing the perovskite surface to be more positive due to partial negative charge movement from the bulk to the surface leading to an additional interfacial dipole toward the surface. [33] Moreover, ¹HNMR confirms the interaction of perovskite with the HTL and junction quality. [33b]

Figure 2. (a) ^1H NMR of CsFAMA (Blue) and CsFAMA-TBAPF (Red) in DMSO (400 MHz, d_6), (b) the magnification of ^1H NMR at 7.80-7.90 ppm and at 8.40-9.20 ppm of d_6 solvent.

The chemical structure of TBAPF, schematic representation of perovskite surface passivation with TBAPF molecule, and hydrogen bonding interaction between the hydrogen of organic ammonium cation and fluorine atoms in TBAPF (Figure 3).

To decipher the elemental distribution on the surface of perovskite after passivation and the interaction between the passivation layer and the perovskite, XPS measurements were performed (Figure 4).

Figure 3. The passivation mechanism of mixed perovskite in the presence of TBAPF: a) Chemical structure of TBAPF. b) Schematic representation of perovskite surface passivation with TBAPF molecule. c) The hydrogen bonding interaction between the hydrogen of organic ammonium cation and fluorine atoms in TBAPF

The core-level peaks regarding F, Pb, and N are presented in Figure 4a-d. The prominent peak at 686.6 eV is assigned to F 1s, which can be attributed to the existence of TBAPF on the surface of the perovskite film (Figure 4a). The two peaks at 137.96 and 142.82 eV in CsFAMA film related to $4f_{7/2}$ and $4f_{5/2}$, respectively, are shifted to lower binding energy upon TBAPF treatment (137.74 and 142.6 eV, respectively). Similarly, two distinct $1d_{5/2}$ (619.28 eV) and $1d_{3/2}$ (630 eV) peaks were found to be shifted

Figure 4. High-resolution X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HR-XPS) of (a) F 1s, (b) Pb 4f for CsFAMA and CsFAMA/TBAPF. HR-XPS of N 1s for (c) CsFAMA and (d) CsFAMA/TBAPF.

to lower binding energy after TBAPF treatment (618.61 and 630.09 eV, respectively) as shown in Figure S2. This behavior is related to the interaction of electron-rich fluorine atoms and perovskite, which can release electrons under lower binding energy. [34] [35]

The components in N1s spectra at 400.36 and 401.75 eV can be assigned to $\text{C}=\text{NH}_2^+$ and $\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$, respectively. Upon TBAPF passivation, the aforementioned peaks appeared at 399.95 and 401.82 eV, respectively, where the $\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$ peak becomes more prominent owing to ammonium in TBAPF (Figure 4c-d). The interaction of TBAPF with perovskite was further studied using FTIR spectroscopy in attenuated transmission reflection (ATR) mode in the range of $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Figure S3). The transmission signals at 1100 cm^{-1} & 900 cm^{-1} correspond to C-N stretching and at around $3450-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to N-H stretching arise from the FA^+/MA^+ cation and the single detected at around 1711 cm^{-1} represent symmetric C=N stretching from FA^+ in perovskite. [36],[37] Similar vibrational peaks were found in the TBAPF-treated perovskite showing the existence of the perovskite phase. However, the stretching related to N-H and C-N was detected to be enhanced and broadened in the case of perovskite treated with TBAPF, which can be ascribed to the possible interaction of tetra-n-butyl ammonium cation and organic cation in the perovskite. According to the SDDBS (spectral database for organic compounds, SDDBS No: 10320), the main peak of TBAPF arises at 842 cm^{-1} , however, the corresponding main signal of TBAPF cannot be distinguished in the TBAPF-treated perovskite as it falls in the intense C-N stretching region of the perovskite.

To investigate the effect of passivation on solar cell's performance, we probed with different concentrations of TBAPF (0.5 mM, 1mM, 1.5mM, and 2mM, Table S1) in *n-i-p* configuration with the architecture of FTO/TiO_2 (blocking & mesoporous- TiO_2)/CsFAMA/TBAPF/PTAA/Au (Figure 5a) and the cross-sectional SEM image of the PSC with 1mM passivation layer is shown in Figure 5b. The PSCs performance of the champion device using 1mM TBAPF and the control device is listed in Table 1. It can be deduced that the passivated PSCs show improved performance with a PCE of **17.70%** with only 1mM of the TBAPF while the control device exhibited a PCE of **16.90%** without TBAPF. The increased FF in the case of the TBAPF passivated

device suggests the filling of grain boundaries by passivation and thus improving the homogeneous distribution of HTL. Moreover, the V_{oc} increases by 19 mV (Figure 5c and Table 1). Statistical data of PSCs using different concentrations of TBAPF are presented in Table S1.

Figure 5. (a) Device architecture adopted in this work, (b) cross-sectional SEM image of the passivated device, (c) J - V characteristics of the n - i - p device with passivation (1mM), Reverse scan, (d) EQE spectra of the corresponding champion device shown in c, (e) Steady-state photocurrent density of the PSCs during the 360s measured at 0.8 V near to MPP, (f) Steady-state PL of CsFAMA, CsFAMA/PTAA and CsFAMA/TBAPF/PTAA films.

The external quantum efficiency (EQE) reached about 87.54% and 84.44% for passivated and control devices respectively which covers the range from 300 – 900 nm (Figure 5d). However, there is no shift in the spectra, which is following our optical absorption measurements. The integrated current (J_{sc}) obtained from the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of control and passivated devices show 20.35 mAcm^{-2} and 21.24 mAcm^{-2} , which is in agreement with the J_{sc} measured from the J - V curve (Figure 5c) and are within marginal experimental error and light source mismatch. Negligible hysteresis is noted for TBAPF-treated PSCs, while the control device suffers from hysteresis compared with passivated one (Table 1 and Figure S4). We measured the steady-state photocurrent density at 0.8 V near MPP under AM 1.5G 100 mW/cm^2 continuous illumination in ambient conditions for 300 s. The evolution of the photocurrent density for 300s suggests its stability (Figure 5e). Further, to deduce the role of TBAPF in hole extraction from the perovskite to HTL, steady-state photoluminescence (PL) measurements were performed. Compare to pristine perovskite, passivated perovskite showed higher PL quenching in the presence of PTAA confirming that TBAPF facilitates hole transportation to the HTL (Figure 5f).

Figure 6 (a) Mott-Schottky plots measured at 10 kHz under dark. (b) Dark current density-voltage (J_d - V) characteristics of control and TBAPF passivated devices. Space-charge-limited current (SCLC) vs. voltage of devices with the structure of (c) FTO/PEDOT:PSS/perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au, (d) FTO/PEDOT:PSS/perovskite/TBAPF/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au, (e) FTO/TiO₂/perovskite/PCBM/Au, and (f) FTO/TiO₂/perovskite/TBAPF/PCBM/Au.

Further, Mott-Schottky investigation was performed at 10 kHz under dark conditions (Figure 6a). The interfacial built-in potential (V_{bi}) was derived from the intercept on the voltage axis in the depletion layer capacitance (C_{dl}) region.^[38] The obtained V_{bi} of the TBAPF-based PSC was derived to be 892.1 mV, which is considerably higher than that of the control device (736.4 mV) and could efficiently drive the force for the separation of photogenerated charge carriers.

The J - V characteristics of the PSCs in dark were measured for control and passivated devices and the semi-logarithmic J - V plots are shown (Figure 6b). The reverse saturation current density (J_0) and ideality factor (n_{id}) can be evaluated by fitting the exponential region of the semi-logarithmic curve with the Shockley ideal diode equation. The values of the [n_{id} , J_0] were [3.06, 6.75 $\mu\text{A/cm}^2$] and [2.45, 0.225 $\mu\text{A/cm}^2$] for the control and TBAPF passivated PSC, respectively (Figure 6b). Compared with the control, passivated PSC showed a lower value of leakage current, and the ideality factor indicates reduced interfacial recombination and improved charge transportation.

The charge carrier mobility and defect density of perovskite films were investigated by the space-charge-limited-current (SCLC) method from electron only (FTO/TiO₂/CsFAMA/with or without TBAPF/PCBM/Au) and hole only device (FTO/PTAA/CsFAMA/with or without TBAPF/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au). The current density-voltage curves (Figure 6 c-f) under dark conditions are separated into three regions: Ohmic linear

Table 1. Photovoltaic parameters derived from J - V measurements of control and TBAPF treated device in n - i - p configuration measured in the reverse direction.

Device	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R_s (Ω)	R_{sh} (k Ω)	HI
TBAPF 1mM	1055	21.33	78.63	17.70	35.94	446.44	0.06
control	1036	21.00	77.62	16.90	41.52	39.95	0.13

relation, trap-filled limited (TFL) region, and the SCLC region. [39] The trap-state density (N_{trap}) was determined by the following equation, [40]

$$N_{trap} = \frac{2V_{TFL}\epsilon_0\epsilon}{eL^2},$$

where, V_{TFL} was extracted from the intersection between the Ohmic and TFL regions, ϵ_0 is vacuum permittivity, ϵ is the relative dielectric constant of CsFAMA perovskite, which is taken as 41.5 from the previous report, e is the electron charge and L is the perovskite film thickness (420 nm). [38] The electron and hole trap densities in the perovskite films are calculated to be 2.86×10^{15} and 2.99×10^{15} cm⁻³ respectively upon the TBAPF passivation layer, which is much lower than the control PSCs with 4.13×10^{15} cm⁻³ of electron trap density and 5.25×10^{15} cm⁻³ of hole trap density. This result further proves that the trap states have been effectually filled by the addition of the TBAPF at grain boundaries, which is beneficial for the proper charge transfer dynamics in the PSCs.

The charge dynamics in the PSCs upon the addition of the TBAPF layer were further studied by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) under dark conditions. The EIS was fitted with the equivalent circuit (insert in Figure S5a) including a series resistance (R_s), a charge transport resistance (R_{ctr}), and a recombination resistance (R_{rec}) at the perovskite/HTL interface, together with two constant phase elements ($CPE1$ and $CPE2$) related to carrier diffusion in the perovskite and selective layers. Notably, the device with TBAPF interlayer exhibits reduced R_{ctr} from 31.05 to 11.04 Ω compared with the control device, which is beneficial to enhance the efficient charge transfer at the perovskite/HTL interface. Meanwhile, at the same potential bias, the device with the interlayer shows significantly enhanced R_{rec} (from 263.9 to 363.6 Ω), ascribing a suppressed charge annihilation at the interface. [12b] Further, it is noted from Figure S5b that R_{ctr} of the control device is higher than that of the device with TBAPF at a given potential bias range, the relative trend of which is following the series resistance (R_s) derived from J - V curve. At the same potential bias range, the target device is featured by a higher R_{rec} than the control device (Figure S5c), which is in good agreement with the shunt resistance (R_{sh}) obtained from the J - V curve. The impact of the TBAPF interlayer on charge lifetime (τ) was studied using Bode EIS spectra at 0.95 V under dark conditions, which also represents the frequency dependence of dielectric features (Figure S6). The peak frequency (f_p) of the electrochemical reaction in the charge-transfer process, which follows the relationship of $\tau = 1/(2\pi f_p)$, can be derived from the $-Z''$ vs frequency spectrum. [39] The TBAPF-based PSC shows a longer charge lifetime (13.91 μ s) compared to that in the control device (10.88 μ s), indicating

mitigated charge recombination at perovskite/PTAA interface upon TBAPF treatment.

The long-term stability of PSCs was conducted on unencapsulated devices (RH 45-65% at room temperature) measured at a constant voltage of 0.8 V near MPP under continuous 1 sun-calibrated white LED light as shown in Figure 7a. Initially, the control device shows a rapid current density drop, losing 70% of its initial photo-current density after 93 h, while the device incorporating TBAPF maintains 80% of its initial current density for around 155h. This stems from the presence of hydrogen bonding to decrease the recombination and ion migration. The thermal stability of the device upon TBAPF was further studied by collecting the photocurrent at a fixed voltage of 0.8 V for devices after being maintained at 85 $^{\circ}$ C for 8h (Figure 7 b, c). The control device shows reduced photocurrent, while the device with TBAPF maintains its initial photo-current throughout the test.

We performed a surface hydrophobicity investigation by measuring the water contact angle. Contact angle measurement shows (Figures 7d and e) that for the perovskite surface treated with TBAPF, the contact angle increases by 27 $^{\circ}$, and this data confirms the fluorinated atoms and long alkyl chain have a prominent effect to increase the hydrophobicity of the perovskite surface.

Figure 7. a) Maximum power point (MPP) tracking for the control and TBAPF treated perovskite solar cells without encapsulation under calibrated 1 sun (100 mW/cm²) illumination at 27 $^{\circ}$ C and RH 45-65% conditions., Current density at MPP for the (b) control and (c) with TBAPF devices before and after heating at 85 $^{\circ}$ C for 8h (un-encapsulated), contact angle measurements (d) pristine CsFAMA perovskite, (e) 1mM TBAPF treated CsFAMA perovskite

Conclusion

In conclusion, we probed the effect of a commercial aliphatic organic salt as the passivating agent for mixed perovskite that improves the PV performance of perovskite solar cells along with the stability against moisture. For the optimized TBAPF treated devices, the efficiency was improved compared to the control devices without TBAPF. TBAPF effectively passivates the grain

boundaries and surface together through hydrogen bonding as indicated by proton NMR measurements. Suppression of surface defects and mitigation of interfacial charge recombination is suggested by electrical measurement and the recombination resistance in the unpassivated solar cells is lower. The passivated perovskites registered a considerably improved V_{oc} and FF. We showed that the perovskite interacts strongly with the passivation layer through hydrogen bonding, amplifies the stability, suppresses non-radiative recombination, and improves the overall performance of the PSCs. Moreover, the presence of fluorine atoms and four long alkyl chains in the TBAPF improves the hydrophobicity of the perovskite and enhances the long-term stability of the devices by preventing moisture and oxygen penetration into the perovskite.

Experimental Section

Materials. The chemicals for perovskite were purchased from Dyesol except for lead iodide (99.99%), Cesium iodide (99.99%), and bathocuproine (BCP) (96%) which were obtained from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI) and were used as such. Tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF) and solvents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and were used without further purification. PTAA ($M_n = 5000$ -15000 by GPC) was procured from Xi'an Polymer Light Technology Corp. Chlorobenzene (CB, 99 %), isopropanol (IPA, 99.9 %), anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.8 %), and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8 %) were purchased from Acros Organics.

***n-i-p* device fabrication.** The laser-etched FTO-coated glasses (NSG10) were sequentially cleaned via ultra-sonication with Hellmanex II solution (2 vol.%), deionized water, acetone, ethanol, and isopropanol for 20 min each step followed by drying using compressed air. The dried substrates were further treated with UV-ozone for 20 min before device fabrication. TiO_2 compact layer was deposited using spray pyrolysis at 500 °C employing titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetyl acetonate) precursor solution (75% in 2-propanol) diluted in anhydrous ethanol with a volume ratio of 1:19 using oxygen as the carrier gas, followed by annealing for another 30 min at 500 °C to acquire the anatase phase. TiO_2 mesoporous layer was spin-coated using TiO_2 nanoparticles dispersion (30 NRD from Dyesol, 1:8 w/v in anhydrous ethanol) at 4000 rpm (2000 rpm/s acceleration) for 30 s at room temperature, followed by progressive heating steps until 500 °C for 30 min. The coated substrates were transferred immediately to the argon-filled glovebox under controlled moisture and oxygen conditions after cooling down to 80 °C (H_2O level: <1 ppm and O_2 level: <10 ppm) to prevent moisture absorption to ETM layers. The triple-cation perovskite [$CS_{0.1}(FA_{0.9}MA_{0.1})_{0.9}Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})_3$] layers were deposited through a one-step method according to the previous report.^[41] Briefly, the perovskite precursor solution, containing CsI (0.10M), FAI (1.05 M), PbI_2 (1.24 M), MABr (0.12 M), and $PbBr_2$ (0.12 M) in an anhydrous solvent mixture of DMF and DMSO ($v/v = 4/1$) was spin-coated with chlorobenzene-based antisolvent method (110 μ L of chlorobenzene was dripped 10s before ending the spin-coating program) followed by annealing at 100 °C for 1 h. To achieve the interfacial layer, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2 mM TBAPF solution in a mixed solvent (*o*-dichlorobenzene: isopropanol = 97:3 v/v) was spin-coated on the perovskite film at room temperature at 5000 rpm for 15 s and then, the substrates were heat-treated for 30 s at 100 °C. Hole transport material (HTM) was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of PTAA in 1mL toluene together with 4 μ L of 4-*tert*-butylpyridine and 10 μ L of bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide lithium salt (120 mg in 1 mL acetonitrile). 35 μ L of HTM solution was dropped on the TBAPF layer and was spin-coated at 5000 rpm for 20 s. Au electrode (80 nm) was thermally evaporated under a pressure of 2×10^{-6} Torr.

Thin-film characterization. The thin layer of passivation was characterized by spectroscopic techniques such as UV-vis, XRD, and SEM. XPS experiments were carried out on a SPECS system (Berlin, Germany)

equipped with Phoibos 150 1D-DLD analyzer with monochromated Al K α radiation (1486.7 eV). The wide scan is performed with the step energy of 1 eV (dwell time: 0.1 s, pass energy: 80 eV), and a detailed analysis of the elements was performed using 0.08 eV step energy (dwell time: 0.1 s, pass energy: 30 eV) with an electron exit angle of 90°. The spectra were adjusted using CasaXPS 2.3.16 software, which models Gauss-Lorentzian contributions. The absorption spectra and PL steady-state measurements were acquired with the help of a UV-vis-IR spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer) and a fluorescence spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer Instrument J&M Tides), respectively. Cross and top-view microstructures were acquired by a Hitachi S-4800 scanning electron microscope. 1H NMR spectra were recorded with a Varian Mercury 400 MHz spectrometer in d_6 (DMSO) solvent. X-ray diffractograms were recorded using a D8 Advance diffractometer from Bruker (Bragg-Brentano geometry, with an X-ray tube Cu K α , $\lambda = 1.5406$ Å).

Device characterization. Current density-voltage (*J-V*) curves are performed using an Oriel solar simulator (Newport, 3A) producing 1 sun AM1.5G (1000 Wm^{-2}) sunlight. The generated photocurrent was recorded at a scan rate of 100 mV/s (pre-sweep delay: 10s) with the help of a Keithley 2400 source meter and a black metal mask (0.09 cm^2) is used over the active area of the device. IPCE measurements were carried out using a 150 W xenon lamp attached to a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4 m monochromator, and IPCE was recorded for every 5 nm wavelength interval. Impedance spectroscopy was performed in the frequency range of 2MHz-1Hz under the perturbation of a 20 mV ac signal using a Biologic SP300 potentiostat in a faradaic chamber, and data analysis were performed using Biologic's EC Lab software. SCLC measurements were conducted in forward bias with a 100 mV/s scan rate.

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Authors Contributions

A.G and N.H.H. contributed equally to this work. A.G made the experiments and PV characterization, N.H.H. fabricated the devices and made SCLC measurements, and analyzed and interpreted the result of SCLC, EIS, and XPS measurements. S.K. and S.A. supervised and directed the research. All authors contributed to the draft.

Keywords:

Interface engineering • Improved stability • 3-D perovskite • Tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate • H-bonding • Trap density

References

- [1] Z.-K. Tan, R. S. Moghaddam, M. L. Lai, P. Docampo, R. Higler, F. Deschler, M. Price, A. Sadhanala, L. M. Pazos, D. Credgington, F. Hanusch, T. Bein, H. J. Snaith, R. H. Friend, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* **2014**, *9*, 687-692.
- [2] Z. Wang, R. Yu, C. Pan, Z. Li, J. Yang, F. Yi, Z. L. Wang, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 8401.
- [3] X. Y. Chin, D. Cortecchia, J. Yin, A. Bruno, C. Soci, *Nat. Commun.* **2015**, *6*, 7383.

- [4] H. Zhu, Y. Fu, F. Meng, X. Wu, Z. Gong, Q. Ding, M. V. Gustafsson, M. T. Trinh, S. Jin, X. Y. Zhu, *Nat. Mater.* **2015**, *14*, 636-642.
- [5] Y.-S. Chen, J. S. Manser, P. V. Kamat, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 974-981.
- [6] a) J. Jeong, M. Kim, J. Seo, H. Lu, P. Ahlawat, A. Mishra, Y. Yang, M. A. Hope, F. T. Eickemeyer, M. Kim, Y. J. Yoon, I. W. Choi, B. P. Darwich, S. J. Choi, Y. Jo, J. H. Lee, B. Walker, S. M. Zakeeruddin, L. Emsley, U. Rothlisberger, A. Hagfeldt, D. S. Kim, M. Grätzel, J. Y. Kim, *Nature* **2021**, *592*, 381-385; b) S. Kazim, M. K. Nazeeruddin, M. Grätzel, S. Ahmad, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2014**, *53*, 2812-2824; c) Y. Rui, Z. Jin, X. Fan, W. Li, B. Li, T. Li, Y. Wang, L. Wang, J. Liang, *Mater. Futures* **2022**, *1*, 045101; d) Y. Li, H. Wu, W. Qi, X. Zhou, J. Li, J. Cheng, Y. Zhao, Y. Li, X. Zhang, *Nano Energy* **2020**, *77*, 105237.
- [7] J. Barbé, A. Pockett, V. Stoichkov, D. Hughes, H. K. H. Lee, M. Carnie, T. Watson, W. C. Tsoi, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2020**, *8*, 1715-1721.
- [8] R. F. Hossain, M. Min, L.-C. Ma, S. R. Sakri, A. B. Kaul, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.* **2021**, *5*, 34.
- [9] a) D. Zhao, S. Dai, M. Li, Y. Wu, L. Zheng, Y. Wang, D.-Q. Yun, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2021**, *4*, 10646-10655; b) A. Ghaderian, M. Pegu, N. H. Hemasiri, P. Huang, S. Ahmad, S. Kazim, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2022**, *10*, 476-484; c) M. Pegu, A. Ghaderian, S. Ahmad, S. Kazim, *ChemPlusChem* **2022**, *87*, e202200021.
- [10] a) J. Hu, I. W. H. Oswald, S. J. Stuard, M. M. Nahid, N. Zhou, O. F. Williams, Z. Guo, L. Yan, H. Hu, Z. Chen, X. Xiao, Y. Lin, Z. Yang, J. Huang, A. M. Moran, H. Ade, J. R. Neilson, W. You, *Nat. Commun.* **2019**, *10*, 1276; b) X. Wang, Y. Xu, H. Zhang, Z. Yan, Y. Jing, X. Liu, J. Wu, Z. Lan, *Adv. Sustain. Syst.* **2022**, *6*, 2200074.
- [11] H. Min, D. Y. Lee, J. Kim, G. Kim, K. S. Lee, J. Kim, M. J. Paik, Y. K. Kim, K. S. Kim, M. G. Kim, *Nature* **2021**, *598*, 444-450.
- [12] a) N. H. Hemasiri, S. Kazim, S. Ahmad, *Nano Energy* **2020**, *77*, 105292; b) N. Harindu Hemasiri, S. Kazim, S. Ahmad, *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2021**, *9*, 9865-9873.
- [13] M. Saliba, T. Matsui, J.-Y. Seo, K. Domanski, J.-P. Correa-Baena, M. K. Nazeeruddin, S. M. Zakeeruddin, W. Tress, A. Abate, A. Hagfeldt, M. Grätzel, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2016**, *9*, 1989-1997.
- [14] G. Kim, H. Min, K. S. Lee, D. Y. Lee, S. M. Yoon, S. I. Seok, *Science* **2020**, *370*, 108-112.
- [15] L. N. Quan, M. Yuan, R. Comin, O. Voznyy, E. M. Beauregard, S. Hoogland, A. Buin, A. R. Kirmani, K. Zhao, A. Amassian, D. H. Kim, E. H. Sargent, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 2649-2655.
- [16] X. Zhang, X. Ren, B. Liu, R. Munir, X. Zhu, D. Yang, J. Li, Y. Liu, D.-M. Smilgies, R. Li, Z. Yang, T. Niu, X. Wang, A. Amassian, K. Zhao, S. Liu, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2017**, *10*, 2095-2102.
- [17] H. Tsai, W. Nie, J.-C. Blancon, C. C. Stoumpos, R. Asadpour, B. Harutyunyan, A. J. Neukirch, R. Verduzco, J. J. Crochet, S. Tretiak, L. Pedesseau, J. Even, M. A. Alam, G. Gupta, J. Lou, P. M. Ajayan, M. J. Bedzyk, M. G. Kanatzidis, A. D. Mohite, *Nature* **2016**, *536*, 312-316.
- [18] Z. Ni, C. Bao, Y. Liu, Q. Jiang, W.-Q. Wu, S. Chen, X. Dai, B. Chen, B. Hartweg, Z. Yu, Z. Holman, J. Huang, *Science* **2020**, *367*, 1352-1358.
- [19] H. Li, X. Wang, T. Zhang, X. Gong, Q. Sun, H. Pan, Y. Shen, S. Ahmad, M. Wang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, *29*, 1903293.
- [20] H. Ren, S. Yu, L. Chao, Y. Xia, Y. Sun, S. Zuo, F. Li, T. Niu, Y. Yang, H. Ju, B. Li, H. Du, X. Gao, J. Zhang, J. Wang, L. Zhang, Y. Chen, W. Huang, *Nat. Photonics* **2020**, *14*, 154-163.
- [21] M. Jeong, I. W. Choi, E. M. Go, Y. Cho, M. Kim, B. Lee, S. Jeong, Y. Jo, H. W. Choi, J. Lee, J.-H. Bae, S. K. Kwak, D. S. Kim, C. Yang, *Science* **2020**, *369*, 1615-1620.
- [22] M. M. Byranvand, M. Saliba, *Sol. RRL* **2021**, *5*, 2100295.
- [23] W.-Q. Wu, P. N. Rudd, Q. Wang, Z. Yang, J. Huang, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, 2000995.
- [24] a) H. Xie, Z. Wang, Z. Chen, C. Pereyra, M. Pols, K. Galkowski, M. Anaya, S. Fu, X. Jia, P. Tang, D. J. Kubicki, A. Agarwalla, H.-S. Kim, D. Prochowicz, X. Borrísé, M. Bonn, C. Bao, X. Sun, S. M. Zakeeruddin, L. Emsley, J. Arbiol, F. Gao, F. Fu, H. I. Wang, K.-J. Tielrooij, S. D. Stranks, S. Tao, M. Grätzel, A. Hagfeldt, M. Lira-Cantu, *Joule* **2021**, *5*, 1246-1266. b) X. Li, M. Ibrahim Dar, C. Yi, J. Luo, M. Tschumi, S. M. Zakeeruddin, M. K. Nazeeruddin, H. Han, M. Grätzel, *Nat. Chem.* **2015**, *7*, 703-711.
- [25] a) Q. Zhou, C. Zuo, Z. Zhang, P. Gao, L. Ding, *J. Semicond.* **2022**, *43*, 010202; b) X. Wang, K. Rakstys, K. Jack, H. Jin, J. Lai, H. Li, C. S. K. Ranasinghe, J. Saghaei, G. Zhang, P. L. Burn, *Nat. Commun.* **2021**, *12*, 1-10; c) B. Yang, J. Suo, F. Di Giacomo, S. Olthof, D. Bogachuk, Y. Kim, X. Sun, L. Wagner, F. Fu, S. M. Zakeeruddin, A. Hinsch, M. Grätzel, A. Di Carlo, A. Hagfeldt, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2021**, *6*, 3916-3923.
- [26] K. M. M. Salim, T. M. Koh, D. Bahulayan, P. C. Harikesh, N. F. Jamaludin, B. Febriansyah, A. Bruno, S. Mhaisalkar, N. Mathews, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, *3*, 1068-1076.
- [27] S. Bai, P. Da, C. Li, Z. Wang, Z. Yuan, F. Fu, M. Kawecky, X. Liu, N. Sakai, J. T.-W. Wang, S. Huettner, S. Buecheler, M. Fahlman, F. Gao, H. J. Snaith, *Nature* **2019**, *571*, 245-250.
- [28] M. Pegu, S. Kazim, T. Buffeteau, D. M. Bassani, S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, *13*, 48219-48227.
- [29] J. Tang, L. Liu, Z. Yu, J. Du, X. Cai, M. Zhang, M. Zhao, L. Bai, Z. Gai, S. Cui, X. Li, T. Jiu, *Adv. Sustain. Syst.* **2022**, *6*, 2100510.
- [30] R. Garai, M. A. Afroz, R. K. Gupta, P. K. Iyer, *Adv. Sustain. Syst.* **2020**, *4*, 2000078.
- [31] a) M. A. Ruiz-Preciado, D. J. Kubicki, A. Hofstetter, L. McGovern, M. H. Futscher, A. Ummadisingu, R. Gershoni-Poranne, S. M. Zakeeruddin, B. Ehrler, L. Emsley, J. V. Milić, M. Grätzel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 1645-1654; b) A. Abate, M. Saliba, D. J. Hollman, S. D. Stranks, K. Wojciechowski, R. Avolio, G. Grancini, A. Petrozza, H. J. Snaith, *Nano Lett.* **2014**, *14*, 3247-3254.
- [32] S. Aharon, A. Dymshits, A. Rotem, L. Etgar, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2015**, *3*, 9171-9178.
- [33] a) Q. Chen, C. Wang, Y. Li, L. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2020**, *142*, 18281-18292; b) L. Canil, J. Salunke, Q. Wang, M. Liu, H. Köbler, M. Flatken, L. Gregori, D. Meggiolaro, D. Ricciarelli, F. De Angelis, M. Stollerfoht, D. Neher, A. Priimagi, P. Vivo, A. Abate, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2021**, *11*, 2101553.
- [34] M. J. Jeong, K. M. Yeom, S. J. Kim, E. H. Jung, J. H. Noh, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2021**, *14*, 2419-2428.
- [35] J. Wu, M. Hu, L. Zhang, G. Song, Y. Li, W. Tan, Y. Tian, B. Xu, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2021**, *422*, 130124.
- [36] J. Yang, Q. Hong, Z. Yuan, R. Xu, X. Guo, S. Xiong, X. Liu, S. Braun, Y. Li, J. Tang, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2018**, *6*, 1800262.
- [37] H. B. Lee, M. K. Jeon, N. Kumar, B. Tyagi, J. W. Kang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, *29*, 1903213.
- [38] M. T. Khan, N. H. Hemasiri, S. Kazim, S. Ahmad, *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2021**, *5*, 6352-6360.
- [39] H. Li, G. Wu, W. Li, Y. Zhang, Z. Liu, D. Wang, S. Liu, *Adv. Sci.* **2019**, *6*, 1901241.
- [40] J. Yuan, L. Zhang, C. Bi, M. Wang, J. Tian, *Solar RRL* **2018**, *2*, 1800188.
- [41] N. Harindu Hemasiri, S. Kazim, L. Calio, S. Paek, M. Salado, G. Pozzi, L. Lezama, M. K. Nazeeruddin, S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Mater. Inter.* **2020**, *12*, 9395-9403